

An Investigation on B.Ed. Student Teachers Attitude Towards Environment in Coimbatore District

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Active participation is not emphasized enough in EE although environmentally responsible behavior can be gradually developed by 1) entry level variables, including the ability to experience and enjoy nature and knowledge of ecology; 2) ownership variables, such as in-depth knowledge and personal investment in the environment; and 3) empowerment variables like internal locus of control and intention and ability to act for the environment. The EE research conducted over the past three decades has focused on changes in the cognitive and affective attributes brought about by EE interventions.

In this work, the review, collection of data, Analysis and interpretation is done and the summary of findings are mentioned for future scope of work.

Review of Literature

Verma, R., & Razdan, A. (2019). Presents over the green school concept and integrate nature into school (mainly through academics, operations, and student/teacher and community engagement) with incorporated natural substance to school educational module. It provides outset of the green school.

Parvez, N., & Agrawal, A. (2019) assesses the sustainability related performance of Indian Higher Education Institutes

ABSTRACT

Environmental crisis is real. Now the time has come when we should be careful. If human society has to endure not just for another century but thousands and thousands of years, we need to imbecile a way of life that can be sustained. The growth of human beings and plants life can only develop fully in friendly environment that is conclusive to growth. Since, the present problems result largely from ignorance and different trend of continued misuse of the environment can, however, be altered by creating awareness among people of how man's activities effect the environment for good or ill. We cannot expect improvement unless attitudes of people change and unless a better generations. Our great need of today is knowledgeable citizens who are conscious of their surrounding and willing to take necessary, social, economic and political steps to assure a better environment for the fulfillment of need and wants of every citizen on the earth. Keeping in view the importance of environment the present study was undertaken to study the awareness among students towards environmental education.

INTRODUCTION

Environmental Education (EE) as: 1) education about the environment, which builds awareness, understanding, and the skills necessary to obtain the understanding; 2) education in (or from) the environment, where learning occurs outside of the classroom, e.g. in nature; and 3) education for the environment, which has objectives related to nature conservation and sustainable development.

(HEIs) based on the parameters and indicators listed under the Sustainability Tracking, Assessment and Rating System (STARS).

Sharma, A., & Joshi, A. (2019). questioned the role of Western education as another form of subtle colonialism in the name of improving education standards. This work analyses the effects of globalization on the education system of a country, especially in the Indian context, as a means of cultural imperialism and stripping away of its rich indigenous culture. This includes an impact on the medium of instruction, curriculum, pedagogical changes and learning outcomes in particular.

Kapur, R. (2019) The main areas that have been taken into account include, the sustainable livelihoods framework, significance of resource use and management of livelihoods, natural resources and livelihoods of individuals in rural areas, utilization of resources, characteristics of rural livelihoods, assets of individuals in rural areas, rural health and rural education.

Sivakami, M., van Eijk, A. M., Thakur, H., Kakade, N., Patil, C., Shinde, S., & Dobhal, A. (2019). Presents awareness about menarche, items used for menstruation, and facilitators on girls' experience of menstruation in regular

schools and compared with model schools. Factors associated with school absence during menstruation were explored using multivariate analysis.

Sathiakumar, N., Tipre, M., Wickremasinghe, R., Bhat, V., Kadir, M. M., Coggon, D., & Smith, T. L. (2019). demand for trained public health professionals in South Asia is enormous and growing, which created a unique opportunity for a Fogarty International Center-funded University of Alabama at Birmingham-South Asia [Aga Khan University, Pakistan; Manipal Academy of Higher Education, India; and University of Kelaniya, Sri Lanka] international research training in environmental and occupational health (ITREOH) programme.

Khan, S., & Kotharkar, R. (2018). Environ- behaviour studies have proved the power of the environmental container to impact inhabitants in a significant way. This paper is part of an on-going doctoral research on evaluating building performance of urban Indian schools using Post Occupancy Evaluation as a major tool through its primary users- the students.

Jain, K., Sharma, S., Prajna, S. C., & Jain, V. (2018). Increasing antisocial and violent behaviors in adolescents and young adults present serious challenges for public health. The present study was undertaken to assess levels of aggressiveness for detecting highly aggressive children in sample populations of primary school children in an urban setting and determine significant bio sociocultural risk-modifying factors in this scenario.

Jose, P. D. (2016). Sustainability issues, given their potential scale of impact and urgency, have captured the imagination of both corporations and academic institutions everywhere. This paper examines how such problems and their potential solutions have been incorporated into higher education, particularly business school education in India. With over

Sampling Techniques

The sample which was collected from various colleges located in and around Coimbatore is shown as below.

TABLE 1 LIST OF COLLEGES USED FOR DATA COLLECTION

S. No	Name of the Colleges	Number of students
1	C.M.S College of Education, Coimbatore	52
2	Dr. SNS College of Education, Coimbatore	46
3	PGP College of Education, Coimbatore	49
4	Dr. N.G.P. College of Education, Coimbatore	52
5	Hindusthan College of Education, Coimbatore	48
6	GRD College of Education, Coimbatore	53
	Total	300

TABLE 2 DISTRIBUTION OF SAMPLES BASED ON VARIABLES

S. No	Category	Subgroups	Number	%	Total
1	Gender	Male	50	17	300
		Female	250	83	
2	Locality of the institution	Rural	74	25	300
		Urban	226	75	
3	Education Qualification	PG	52	17	300
		UG	248	83	
4	Type of Family	Joint	57	19	300
		Nuclear	243	81	
5	Type of Group	Arts	117	39	300
		Science	183	61	

3,600 business schools in the public and private sector, business education in India has proliferated.

Rao, P., & Patil, Y. (2015). An environment and sustainability have caught the attention of various sections of society as issues threatening the very fabric of global business and polity. Climate change as a major environmental challenge is now at the center stage of attention by world leaders, academia, business and industry and civil society.

Shivakumara, K., Sangeetha Mane, R., Diksha, J., & Nagara, O. (2015). Aimed in the present study to explore the effect of gender on environmental awareness of the post-graduate students.

Variables of the Study (6)

In research, this term refers to the measurable characteristics, qualities, traits or attributes of a particular individual, object or situation being studied. Nurses use the term variable whether they are conducting, reading or using results of qualitative or quantitative research. Researchers often refer to variable by the terms dependent or independent. Dependent variable represent outcomes of interest and they are affect by independent (i.e predictor) variables. In this study, the investigator follows independent variable and dependent variables.

An independent variable is a variable that is expected to influence the dependent variables. Its value may be changed or altered, which is independent of any other variables. Also the following demographic variables were used as independent variables.

- Gender (Male/Female).
- Locality of the institution (Rural/Urban).
- Food Habit (Vegetarian/Non-Vegetarian).
- Type of Family (Joint/Nuclear).
- Type of Group (Arts/Science).

Research Tool

Tool become another major consideration in an education research. The instrument employed for the collection of data required for the study of any problem is called tool. "Tool employ distinction way of describing and qualifying the data" the important tools of educational research include interview schedule, questionnaire, observation, rating scale, achievement test, proficiency test, psychological tests and sociogram.

Hypothesis of the Study

1. There is no significant level of study on attitude towards awareness of Environmental education among B.Ed. College Students based on their Gender.
2. There is no significant level of study on attitude towards awareness of Environmental education among B.Ed. College Students based on their Locality of the institution.
3. There is no significant level of study on attitude towards awareness of Environmental education among B.Ed. College Students based on their Food Habit.
4. There is no significant level of study on attitude towards awareness of Environmental education among B.Ed. College Students based on their Type of Family.
5. There is no significant level of study on attitude towards awareness of Environmental education among B.Ed. College Students based on their Type of Group.

Analysis and Interpretation of Data

The various hypothesis is analyzed based on the data collected and results are produced in tables and charts.

TABLE 3 Mean Score difference and 't' value of factors related to significant study of level of study on B.Ed. student teachers attitude towards environment in Coimbatore district based on their Gender.

S. No	Gender	N	Mean	Df	t-Value	Result
1	Male	50	3.1200	106	1.6594	Accept
2	Female	250	3.1960			

CHART 1 LEVEL OF STUDY ON B.Ed. STUDENT TEACHERS ATTITUDE TOWARDS ENVIRONMENT IN COIMBATORE DISTRICT BASED ON THEIR GENDER.

TABLE 4 Mean Score difference and 't' value of factors related to significant study of level of study on B.Ed. student teachers attitude towards environment in Coimbatore district based on their Locality of the institution.

S. No	Locality of the institution	N	Mean	Df	t-Value	Result
1	Rural	74	2.8649	192	1.6528	Accept
2	Urban	226	3.2743			

CHART 2 LEVEL OF STUDY ON B.Ed. STUDENT TEACHERS ATTITUDE TOWARDS ENVIRONMENT IN COIMBATORE DISTRICT BASED ON THEIR LOCALITY OF THE INSTITUTION

TABLE 5 Mean Score difference and 't' value of factors related to significant study of level of study on B.Ed. student teachers attitude towards environment in Coimbatore district based on their educational qualification.

S. No	Food Habit	N	Mean	Df	t-Value	Result
1	PG	52	4.7115	286	1.6502	Accept
2	UG	248	4.3548			

CHART 3 LEVEL OF STUDY ON B.Ed. STUDENT TEACHERS ATTITUDE TOWARDS ENVIRONMENT IN COIMBATORE DISTRICT BASED ON THEIR EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATION

TABLE 6 Mean Score difference and t- value of factors related to significant study of level of study on attitude towards awareness of Environmental education among B.Ed. College Students based on their Type of Family

S. No	Type of Family	N	Mean	Df	t-Value	Result
1	Joint	57	3.1228	84	1.6632	Accept
2	Nuclear	243	3.0741			

CHART 4 LEVEL OF STUDY ON B.Ed. STUDENT TEACHERS ATTITUDE TOWARDS ENVIRONMENT IN COIMBATORE DISTRICT BASED ON THEIR TYPE OF FAMILY

TABLE 7 Mean Score difference and 't' value of factors related to significant study of level of study on B.Ed. student teachers attitude towards environment in Coimbatore district based on their Type of Group.

S. No	Type of Group	N	Mean	Df	t-Value	Result
1	Arts	117	3.2650	253	1.6509	Accept
2	Science	183	2.8197			

CHART 5 LEVEL OF STUDY ON B.ED. STUDENT TEACHERS ATTITUDE TOWARDS ENVIRONMENT IN COIMBATORE DISTRICT BASED ON THEIR TYPE OF GROUP.

The table 3 -7 are the values are assed based on SPSS software and the finding are made through chart 1-5. The finding are as bellow.

Summary of the Findings

A study on high school students' level of attitude towards awareness of Environmental education among B.Ed. College Students was studied and the findings reveal that there is no significant in attitude towards awareness of Environmental education among B.Ed. College Students with respect to and no significant in attitude towards awareness of Environmental education among B.Ed.

College Students with respect to **Gender, Education qualification Locality of the institution, Type of Group and Type of Family.**

Conclusion

Perhaps the most important outcome of this study is its demonstration of the considerable amount of research

activity that is currently occurring in the area of learners and learning in environmental education. The review highlights a number of topics relating to B.Ed. College students for which research evidence is currently available. In considering possible implications, however, it should be recognized that research evidence will rarely translate easily into simple ingredients for developing environmental education practice or policy

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PERSONAL DATA SHEET**APPENDICES****PROFORMA FOR BASIC DATA**

1. Name of the Student :
2. Name of the School :
3. Gender : Male Female
4. Locality of the institution : Rural Urban
5. Food Habit : Vegetarian Non-Vegetarian
6. Type of Family : Joint Nuclear
7. Type of Group : Arts Science

INSTRUCTIONS

In the following pages 25 questions are given. Five possible modes of responses are provided, such as strongly agree (SA), Agree (A), Undecided (UD), Probably (P), and Disagree (DA). Read each questions carefully and make a tick mark in any one of the five alternative responses modes, to indicate your level of agreement with the particulars content of the questions. Please be frank and honest in answering. Your answers will be treated confidential and will be used for academic purposes only.

S. No	Statements	Strongly agree SA	Agree A	Un decided UD	Probably P	Disagree DA
	Environmental values:					
1.	... viewing the natural things around me like flowers, trees and clouds give pleasure					
2.	... I'm interested in reading about nature or the environment					
3.	... all things, whether human, animals, plants or stones have the right to exist					
4.	... animals should have legal rights					
5.	... all organisms lives are precious and worth preserving					
6.	... using animals for transportation should be avoided					
7.	... nature must be preserved because God or another super natural force is part of it, even in its non-living aspects					
8.	... in general, raising animals in cage should be forbidden					
9.	... from time to time, I contribute to charity					
10.	... the earth's value does not depend on people; it is valuable in itself					
11.	.. wildness and beauty in the environment has inherent value					
	Environmental intention: I agree that ...					
12.	... I wait until I have a full load before doing my laundry					
13.	... I will use natural products to preserve the environment					
14.	... in future I will reduce the use of plastic products					
15.	... I support financial contribution to environment organization					
16.	... it is our duty to create pollution free environment					
17.	... more controls should be placed on industry and agriculture to protect the quality of the environment even if it means that thing I purchase will cost more					
18.	... I set a positive environmental example for my friends					
19.	... I support candidates for political offices who are concerned about environmental problems and issues					
20.	... I avoid purchasing products that have a negative impact on the environment					